

Understanding The Nexus Between Migration And Exploitation: The Case Study Of Temporary Migrants From Erstwhile Fata, Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 09, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 12, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Migrants, Workers, Exploitation, Living condition, Wages</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5565168</p>	<p><i>People in scores migrate from the developing countries to the developed countries for finding employment and making a better living which in many cases, is hard for them in their own countries. In this article, we tried to explore the varying dimensions of migrants from sub-division Darra, Kohat. This study utilized qualitative approach while interpretive paradigm was explored to explore the problems of migrants through the eyes of migrants themselves. A total of 15 migrants of different age and experiences were recruited through purposive sampling. The collected data was analysed through thematic analysis technique. It was concluded that migrants face numerous problems but one of the most important problem is related to housing or living conditions. The accommodation provided by the employers are usually overcrowded or non-liveable therefore, they have to pay for their own accommodation in order to live peacefully. Furthermore, migrants often experience the issue of delayed wages and discrimination from supervisory as well as managerial staff.</i></p>

Introduction

The history of migration is way ancient as human civilization itself. In prehistoric era the migration of people was not like the modern migration, where people are seeking for employment or political asylum, but they were going to those areas where no one has ever inhabited. They were mostly nomadic and used to go to those places where they can fulfil their needs. According to the American history Cristopher Columbus in 15th century wanted to sail the west until to reach Asia despite of reaching Asia he sailed and discovered the continent America in 1492. It was just example of the migration from the history but, the history of migration is very old (Therese et al, 2008; Howe and Jackson, 2004).

According to the United Nation (2011), it is evaluated that 180 million individuals -approximately 3 percent of the entire world's population- are living in nations in which they were not born. Among these migrants there are millions of profoundly well-educated and skilful individuals who moved to predetermined (developed) nations from poor (developing) nations that already endure from low levels of human capital and talented laborers. Besides, the stream of formal remittances from transients to their relatives in their home nation has displayed a fast and quickening rate of development. In recent times, advance economies are heavily dependent on foreign migrant workers yet their government policies have embedded as well as surfaced components of immigration (Kaur, 2010).

According to the State Bank of Pakistan, the remittance flow has increased 24.7 percent from the last year, reaching to \$2095 million in August 2020. It is the biggest source of external capital for bunch of nations (Arif, 2009). According to Global Development Finance, the international remittances sent back home by these migrant workers have a tremendous impact on the economy of backward countries of Asia, Africa, Latin America, and the Middle East. As a result of these patterns, migration problems have progressively gotten to be the focus of consideration, both in governments of home and host nations, additionally within the development community (World Bank, 2014).

Migrant workers give vital services and support in globalizing our world. They give a diversity of cheap and low-skill services in both public and private segments. They work in several industrial facilities, fish farms, families, plantations, and construction sites and serve as caretakers, servants, cooks, sweepers, workers, and labourers both inside and beyond their nation-state boundaries (Ullah, Khan, & Ali, 2017). According to the Ministry of Overseas Pakistanis and Human Resource Development, around 8.8 million Pakistanis live overseas, with the tremendous, larger part, over 4.7 million people, dwelling within the Middle East, and around 1.2 million, live within the United Kingdom. According to the UN Department of Financial and Social Affairs, Pakistan has the 6th biggest populous country within the world having millions of individuals working abroad to Pakistan.

Literature Review

Individuals are moving for their job from one portion of the world to another. Moreover, it can be due to war, or wilderness. Migrating in search of work is the foremost vital financial contemplations which has been

expanding as the time passes. There are certain components due to which labour moves from home country, and that is their family. The choice of nation of destination was too regularly affected by the presence of an arrange of family and companions who have migrated already to a particular nation (Solimano, 2002).

Movement in look of work altogether progresses the financial standing of left behind family and national economy in common (GOP, 2008). Migrants have more prominent to get cash which frees them from fabric depravation, and are supportive in securing way better wellbeing, and instruction other than survival, food, restoration, and recreation in reaction to normal or man-made circumstances (UN, 2011; Hadi, 1999).

Most of the existing thinks about, which centres on the impacts of relocation on family individuals cleared out behind, have appeared positive affect within the shorter and longer run. The family individuals, who are cleared out behind, utilize settlements for nourishment, security, education, wellbeing protections and vital thought processes to move forward their life for a long time. It moreover straightforwardly contributes to family wage, and encourages them in buying more merchandise, together with satisfying the education and wellbeing care necessity (UN, 2011). Migrants' living conditions were exceptionally essential for the larger part, with most of them living in dormitory-style housing (sharing with a few other laborers) with exterior comforts (tap water and toilets). Despite these conditions, the larger part portrayed the living conditions as satisfactory or great (Hesketh et al., 2008).

Individuals move with the hope of advancement of living condition. Movement in seeking of work essentially makes strides the financial standing of cleared out behind family and national economy in common, however it costs hardship as well (GOP, 2013). Settlements within the shape of cash are found as major commitment in guaranteeing a better status to the cleared out behind family individuals, as they have more prominent access to wealth which frees them from fabric depravation, and are supportive in securing hitter wellbeing, and instruction other than survival, food, restoration and remaking in reaction to characteristic or man-made circumstances. In any case, the left behind families, particularly the guardians and spouse are burdened with extra obligations of caring children (UN, 2011; Hadi, 1999). Most of the existing literature, which concentrate on the impacts of movement on family individuals cleared out behind, have appeared positive affect in both the brief run and long run. The family individuals, who are cleared out behind, utilize migrants' settlements. Settlements are utilized to reimburse advances taken to fund migration or education, and protections and key thought processes. It also straightforwardly contributes to family pay, permitting families to purchase more resources; empowers higher speculation in commerce; and encourage buying more products, counting education and wellbeing inputs (UN, 2011).

Managers' recognitions and states of mind are vulnerable to choose blunders. Cases of such mistakes incorporate the "similar to me" impact, alluding to the more favourable assessment of a candidate whose mind-set, identity characteristics, or nationality is comparable to the evaluator's (Almeida et al., 2012), and stereotyping, specifying to generalization and assessing candidates based on sex, race, appearance, dress or complement (Murray and Ali, 2017). Supervisors have a more complex assignment when evaluating migrant applications (e.g. supervisors are not recognizable with the migrant's past managers and educational organizations; social contrasts and dialect obstructions can lead to lower level of communication) and, so, are indeed more vulnerable to choose mistakes in this setting. Due to the higher level of complexity a modern line of inquire about is required to look at how organizational decision-makers see and survey migrant laborers. Whereas the impacts of organizational forms on work environment disparity have been examined, small is known almost how supervisors, in specific, may shape the work results of migrant candidates and workers (Castilla, 2011).

Directors are agentic on-screen characters, and their attitudes and convictions essentially influence HR hones. The existing writing records and experimentally confirms that managers' attitudes towards specific bunches can impact the determination prospects of candidates having a place to those bands. For occurrence, assessment of groups such as crippled individuals (Hernandez et al., 2006; Howe and Jackson, 2004), migrants with domestic nations (Stangej et al., 2018) and people of a certain race (Pager and Karafin, 2009) can be influenced by manager's state of mind. Accepting that managers' states of mind can predisposition selection choices, we point to investigate the determinants of these states of mind. Such inquire about ought to help organizations to define a more comprehensive contracting prepare, and to recognize and expel unjustifiable administrative demeanours. The outcomes ought to also aid migrants understand organizations' appraisal criteria, in this way making a difference them to create way better career administration techniques for progressing their careers within the host nation.

According to the existing writings, media reports and other sources, transient workers are abused in most locales of the world particularly in developed nations as cheap labour. In various cases, the emigrant workers conclusion up not only losing the speculations that they made in getting their employments in host country, but moreover their essential human respect, wellbeing, and, in a few awful cases, indeed their lives (Khafagy, 1982). All as well regularly, they are denied of pay their compensations on time, constrained by the manger to work more than their real time outline, cleared out in barbaric living conditions, denied the flexibility to move or alter their occupations and begin new one, and in most cases, they are subjected to physical and at

some point sexual mishandle. Their abuse damages both globally established standards and essential standards of the humankind that serve as the establishment of profound quality and law in these states (Hadi and Kamal, 1997).

Research objectives:

- To explore the experiences of Pakistani migrants in United Arab Emirates
- To know about the living conditions of migrant workers

Research questions:

- What are the experiences of migrant workers?
- How migrant workers are coping with the living problems?

Methodology and Theoretical Framework

Qualitative approach was utilized to conduct this study with migrants from sub-division Darra, Kohat formerly known as FR Kohat. In qualitative approach, interpretive paradigm (Bryman, 2016) was adopted to explore various dimensions of temporary migration and the problems of temporary migrants from sub-division Darra, Kohat. Hence, interpretive paradigm gives the edge of constructing and understanding the problems from the lens of participants. Further, in-depth interviews were conducted with 15 respondents from Darra, Kohat who either worked or were still working in the UAE. All the respondents were recruited through purposive sampling technique. While interviewing the respondents, special care was taken of sensitivity issues and anonymity of the respondents. Moreover, the personal details of the respondents were not collected and the identity of the respondents has been kept secret.

For analysing, thematic analysis was carried out to organize and interpret the collected data. Initially, the interviews were recorded and then transcribed into English manually. The transcriptions were analysed and relevant data were marked and gathered into a section. With indexing the labels, codes were generated and then relevant codes were transformed into themes for interpretation and explanation of the collected data (See Bryman, 2016; Creswell, 2011; Creswell, 2014; Babbie, 2009).

Furthermore, this article draws on the theoretical analysis of Gallagher (2015) migration and exploitation. Migration has been entangled with the exploitation wherein migrants' lives, and well-being are found to be at risk because of the problems involved in the course of and after migration. It is further argued that there is no possible cure to the exploitation associated with the process of migration.

Results and Discussion

Following are the demographic characteristics of the respondents

Age of participants	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 25Y	2	13.3%
25 – 35Y	7	46.6%
35 – 45Y	5	33.3%
More than 45Y	1	6.6%
Total	15	100%

The above table shows that the age of participants ranging from less than 25 to more than 45 years. The majority of migrant workers (i.e. 46.6%) were in the age group of 25 to 35 years while 33.3% of migrant worker were in the age group of 35 to 45 years. Similarly, 13.3% of the participants were in the age group of less than 25 year while 6.6% of the participants were having age of more than 45 years

Duration of Staying Abroad

Monthly Income (PKR)	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 40K	2	13.3%
41-60K	9	60%
61-80K	3	20%
More than 80K	1	6.6%
Total	15	100%

The above table reveals the monthly income of the participants while working mostly as unskilled workers. The majority (i.e. 60%) of migrant workers having monthly income ranging between 41 – 60 thousands approximately equal to 1,000 – 1,200 UAE Dirhams. There were 20% of the workers who said that their income

is ranging between 61 -80 thousand per month. Moreover, 13.3% of the participants reported that their monthly income is less than 40,000 rupees per month. While only one of the participants was earning more than 80 thousand as he was working in corporate sector.

Living condition

Living conditions includes basic elements such as food, shelter, clothes, water, space, sleeping area etc. Majority of the participants were dissatisfied with their accommodation and the money they were paying for. The participant told the researchers that the companies or private sectors we are working in has provide us shelter, but that shelter is not good enough, so the participants added that they are living in private hostels (Dera), for which they pay 500 hundred dirhams for bed and 200 hundred dirhams for monthly food but still the accommodation is problematic and overcrowded.

One participant stated that *“no doubt that our living condition is good compared the facilities we had back home, but it is quite difficult for us to send enough remittance to support our left behind families, to bring balance unwillingly we do over time to feed our left behind”*.

Another participant who was working as a labour told the researcher that I hardly manage to earn 1000 dirhams per month, but the expenditure is very high. The lift behind family thought that we are working in goldmines, and we are earning a lot of money, their demands are high, but no one knows that how hardly we manage as a migrant. They all believe that their living condition is good enough, but the main problem is that they could not get what they came for. They opined that they could manage to earn 40 – 50 thousand per month in Pakistan, they came here to earn more money to support their families. They all were of the view that everything is available, but it is too expensive, and we can hardly manage to keep things in balance. Migrants living conditions were exceptionally essential for the larger part, with most of them living in dormitory-style housing (sharing with a few other laborers) with exterior conveniences (tap water and toilets). Despite these conditions, majority of the migrants compromise on their accommodation for the sake of their jobs (Therese et al., 2008).

Discrimination:

Managers are agentic actors, and their attitudes and convictions altogether influence HR practices. Employer attitude toward migrant workers ispathetic, literature shows that migrant workers are more subjected and vulnerable to be suffer and to be discriminated. While interviewing different migrant worker it reveals that the managers/employers' attitude was not convincing toward the migrants.

One of the participants stated *“the manager attitude is very hash toward us, but in contrast it is very humble and sober toward the other worker. Furthermore, he added that I do not know that why they treat us differently, we all are human beings and we all should be treated equally”*. He also claims that the managers not even consider us as human, but they see us as a machine which ultimately affects our mental and physical health.

Another participant has the view that the migrants are discriminated in every sector. He further added that for example if there is a job advertisement and there are two vacancies available and they hire one Arab and one non- Arab for the same designation. He claims that they will give more opportunities and bonuses to the Arab over a non-Arab despite being more skilful and talented than the Arab.

Another participant gives his thoughts in support of his fellow migrant worker, he told the researcher that in Gulf States it is mandatory for every company/firm that they will hire a local person in company without any skill, they pay them for doing nothing, but it increases the workload on the migrants in a limited wage.

Another participant told the researchers *“Whenever a person is recruited to a company and after some time, he/she want to quit the job and want to work in another place. That company than does not allow the worker to work somewhere else. He argued that a lot of cases are registered but no one is taking actions against them. If someone try to miss with them, they use their approach and cancel the visa of that person and banned him for 5 to 10 years”*.

Managers' attitudes and perceptions are vulnerable to decision blunders. Illustrations of such blunders incorporate the “similar to me” impact, referring to the more favourable assessment of a candidate whose mindset, identity characteristics, or nationality is comparative to the evaluator's (Almeida et al., 2012), and stereotyping, alluding to generalization and evaluating candidates based on gender bases, race, appearance, dress, or language differences (Murray and Ali, 2017). While the impacts of organizational processes on working environment inequality have been explored, small is known about how supervisors, in specific, may shape the work results of migrant employees and workers (Castilla, 2011).

Low and delayed wages:

Migrant workers are more vulnerable to be victimized by the evil of low wages from the companies. But despite of the low wages they are further exploited by the companies in terms of their sweat payment. Majority of the migrants report the same issue in different sectors.

One of the migrant workers share his experience, he told the researchers that I was working in a construction company two months before covid-19 outbreak. I was not paid for three months, and the crisis of covid-19 has also shattered our economic condition. I begged them for payment, but they told me that they

could only pay 50 percent of my salary. I was in great trouble and agreed to receive only 50 percent of my salary.

Another participant also argued about the duty timing. He stated that his duty time is not specified like the company worker or construction site. He was a driver, and any time he can be asked for drive. He was not satisfied with the salary. He argued that the work time is more than what he is paid, and he could hardly manage in it.

All the participants have the same view about the working hours, they argued that we are working for 10 to 12 hours a day, and get only a Friday off, despite all these hardships the salaries/wages are not satisfactory. They also complained about the force work by the companies, they argued that whenever the company gets more projects, it increases the working hours with the concern of the workers.

Within the 2009 report on forced labour, the International Labour Organization estimates that transient laborers are duped of more than \$20 billion a year in terms of opportunity fetched or lost profit due to constrained work. In prior 2005 report, the ILO evaluated those 12.3 million men, women, and children were in a few shapes of constrained work or subjugation throughout the globe. Migrant laborers are subjected to forced work, for illustration, within the sweatshops of China, the families of Hong Kong, the fish farms of Burma, and the clothing businesses of Bangladesh, the plantations of Malaysia, and homes, farms, and construction sites within the Middle East. Migrants are deprived of pay their salaries on time, forced by the manger to work more than their actual time frame (Hadi and Kamal, 1997).

Conclusion

Migrations from origin countries to destination countries has never been an easy task. Many people from Pakistan especially erstwhile FATA migrate to the gulf countries for sake of employment. While analysing living conditions of migrant workers, it is concluded that their living condition was never up to the required standards because of the employers' policies of accommodation They were living in congested space to save some money for their left behind families Furthermore, majority of the participants were paying more money as rent for their living even it was half of their salaries for some of the participants. It is also concluded that the migrant workers are not often get will, but when get ill it is very hard for them to get treatment over there, because the treatment is very expensive, so the migrant workers could not afford it. For treatment purpose the migrants get back to their home countries. With the collected evidence It is concluded from the employer/managers attitude that they were not fair, nor did they support it can also be concluded that migrant workers are poorly treated because of their vulnerability as well as their lack of knowledge about laws of the land and their due rights as employees.

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